

NAVY REQUIREMENTS FOR SPACE-SENSED OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA

CDR D. C. Honhart, USN

Chief of Naval Operations, Naval Oceanography Division (OP-952)

Abstract

This paper deals with the types of atmospheric and oceanographic environmental products required in support of naval warfare. It discusses the quantitative and spatial limitations of environmental data gathered from conventional systems and a look at recent national programs for operational space-borne oceanographic systems. Examples of environmental products with and without space observed data are presented. A brief discussion of the Navy's future plans completes the presentation.

1. Introduction

We watched as the indian darted across the open field disappearing into an adjoining woods. We knew he was there but we couldn't see him. We listened as the submarine worked his way south and west disappearing into the region of the gulf stream. We knew he was there but we couldn't hear him.

In the era of tall masts and wooden ships a naval officer had to be a master in his application of the ocean environment. Winds, waves and currents were the elements of propulsion and tactical maneuvering in battle. With Robert Fulton's development of steam propulsion and the passing of sails, the perception also passed that a capable mariner by necessity must be a master in the application of environmental elements. It is an interesting twist of irony that in the 177 years since Admiral Nelson's victory at Trafalgar, given the advances in ship design, propulsion systems, weapons and tactics, the technical complexities of war at sea once again dictate a keen working knowledge of the ocean environment.

The United States Navy is unique in its operational requirements for the forecasting of atmospheric and oceanographic conditions. To appreciate the magnitude of these requirements one must clearly understand the mission of the Navy to respond to a crisis in any sector of the globe. The required tactical environmental products

include: tactical weather forecasting for flight operations and ship routing, prediction of acoustic conditions for submarine and anti-submarine warfare, mine warfare, underway replenishment, swimmer operations, search and rescue operations, and prediction of polar ice conditions for submarine and surface ship operations; plate 1.

OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA
TACTICAL APPLICATIONS

DATA	OCEANOGRAPHIC PRODUCT	FLEET TACTICAL APPLICATIONS
SEA SURFACE WINDS	SEA SURFACE WIND FIELD ANALYSIS	FLIGHT FORECASTING SHIP ROUTING WAVE AND SURF FORECASTING: • AMPHIBIOUS OPERATIONS • SWIMMER OPS • UNDERWAY REPLENISHMENT CRUISE MISSILE SUPPORT SURFACE AMBIENT NOISE (ASW) RADAR AND ECM RANGE PREDICTIONS
SEA SURFACE TEMP.	OCEAN THERMAL STRUCTURE ANALYSIS MAP OF FRONTS AND EDDIES	LOCATION OF POTENTIAL HIDING PLACES FOR SUBMARINES (FRIENDLY AND UNFRIENDLY) ASW SUPPORT: • SONAR RANGE PREDICTIONS • WEAPONS SETTING • SONAR TOW DEPTHS ACoustic ROUTING OF SURFACE SHIPS AND SUBMARINE
ICE	POLAR ICE FIELD ANALYSIS	SUBMARINE SURFACING INFORMATION NAVIGATION INFORMATION

PLATE 1

2. Global Data Base

There are five basic elements involved in the provision of timely and accurate atmospheric and oceanographic tactical products to support all areas of naval warfare. These are:

1. Scientifically accurate atmospheric and oceanographic forecast models
2. Fast large-capacity computers
3. Global atmospheric and oceanographic data base (real time)
4. Skilled personnel
5. Effective communications

Of the five elements listed, the one which stands alone as the Achilles heel is the global data base. We are faced with two basic problems: First, ocean data is sparse and poorly distributed. Second, the satellite environmental sensors which do exist are designed to see clouds - not through them. As a consequence we simply cannot see the sea surface in areas of considerable tactical importance.

For an actual 24 hour period in 1978, we plotted the number of conventional ocean surface wind observations, (ships, buoys, etc.) received at Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center, Monterey, Calif. versus SEASAT satellite ocean surface winds available during the same period of time, plate 2.

PLATE 2

Look at the ocean basins of immediate tactical concern, the North Atlantic, North Pacific and Indian oceans. What you should carry away from the plate is a feeling for the relative scarcity of data when limited to conventional data sources.

Plate 3 shows the spatical distribution of ocean surface wind observations from ships plotted against those available from the SEASAT satellite for the same 24 hour period of time. Each heavy dot represents one single surface wind observation. These observations came from transoceanic steamers, research ships, fishing vessels, etc. Note the heavy concentration of data in the tactically important water off Japan, and be aware of the fact that 90 to 95 percent of these observations came from non U.S. sources. Now compare the distribution of ship data with the well distributed data from the SEASAT satellite represented by the small dots. Think if you will, in terms of global naval operations; flight weather forecasting, ship routing, weapons systems support, etc.

**NORTH PACIFIC
SURFACE PROJECTION OF
SCATTERMETER DATA COVERAGE
DURING 24-HOUR PERIOD**

PLATE 3

I said we had 2 problems - take a look at plate 4 which shows relative cloud cover. If one concentrates on the Arctic, and the northern parts of the North Atlantic and North Pacific (which are areas of immediate naval concern) one can readily see the limitations placed upon us when we try to ascertain daily oceanographic conditions while limited to the use of infrared and visual satellite sensing systems which cannot see through clouds.

**RELATIVE CLOUD COVER
(POLAR VIEW)**

PLATE 4

3. Tactical Products

Since April of 1981 the Chief of Naval Operations, Director, Naval Oceanography Division (OP-952) has been working to qualitatively and quantitatively demonstrate that the data gathered by an oceanographic satellite would significantly improve the tactical environmental products which were already being provided to the fleet.

The Naval Eastern Oceanography Center at Norfolk, Virginia provides the Atlantic Fleet with an analysis of sea surface temperature patterns. Unfortunately, the only satellite sensor which provides fine detail of sea surface temperature is an infrared system which is blocked by clouds. As a consequence, the oceanography center often goes days or weeks without receiving fine detail data in important operational areas. The data is required to determine the precise location of ocean mesoscale features such as fronts and eddies. Such information permits the on-scene commander to optimize the placement of sonobuoy fields and in general, more effectively deploy ASW assets.

PLATE 5

Plate 5 is an example of the improved sea surface temperature detail that can only be derived from a space borne sensing system. The streamlined isotherms on this vignette represent an analysis of sea surface temperature made without the benefit of data from space borne sensors. The overlaid fine detail isotherm analysis was made from the GOES east satellite infrared sensor. The point is, that it is only when you have such detail as this that fronts/eddies and other mesoscale ocean phenomenon can be mapped.

Many people do not know how well we are doing in this business of weather forecasting. Plate 6 depicts the skill of the Navy atmospheric forecast model, wherein 100 is a perfect forecast and 0 is the skill represented by persistence. (Persistence is a forecast which predicts no change in weather for some specified number of hours/days.) What is obvious, is that there is room for improvement. We have changed analysis and forecast models, experimented with math, upgraded our computers, but the fact of the matter is that skill in forecasting has levelled off. The one important element which has not been significantly improved is the data base.

PLATE 6

The Canadians, at the Atmospheric Environmental Service, Toronto did an excellent, qualitative study on the impact of surface winds derived from the NASA oceanographic research satellite, SEASAT. The most important result of this study was the conclusion that storm fronts and centers could be identified, which could not be identified when limited to ocean surface winds observed from conventional platforms (ships, buoys etc.). This is a considerable result. The potential impact on tactical weather support and battle group or convoy routing is obvious, but consider if you will, the impact on anti-submarine warfare—specifically ASW aircraft operations. Think in terms of wasted fuel and sonobuoy sensors, let alone the ineffective utilization of a valuable ASW asset when the aircraft arrives on scene to discover an adverse sea state which defeats his system before he ever gets started.

SURFACE PRESSURE ANALYSIS
25 AUGUST 1978

PLATE 7

Plate 7 is one example of the work done by the Canadians. Two things are obvious. The first is the identification of a second small storm (bottom chart). The other is the improvement in the shapes of the weather features identified (both storm areas and calm areas). Again, think in terms of tactical weather support, battle group routing and anti-submarine warfare.

Last year the Navy routed 1300 ships (a route is defined as being over 1500 nmi). If a global surface wind sensing system existed such as that flown on the SEASAT satellite, the Navy could conservatively save an additional 163 shipping days per year, (or approximately \$2M in fuel) over that presently saved. One cannot justify a 250 million dollar satellite system in order to save \$2M in fuel oil - but in a wartime scenario 163 shipping days could be critical.

The Arctic has definitely emerged as an important arena for naval operations. Ice information such as ice edge, thickness, age, etc. is important for submarine surfacing, navigation and so forth. Plate 8 shows the considerable difference in the analyzed portion of the ice edge when you do not have a sensor flying which can

sense the edge through clouds. The microwave radiometer which provides this "all weather" capability is also the same sensor required to locate mesoscale ocean features such as fronts and eddies in cloud covered areas.

POLAR ICE EDGE ANALYSIS

PLATE 8

The above discussion focused on but a few examples regarding the importance of environmental products in the execution of naval operations. The true value of accurate environmental data is often hard to assess in terms of cost effectiveness and force multiplier (i.e., how to use your operational forces more effectively). However, the ship that capsizes, broaches, or sustains structural damage, the submarine that goes undetected, or the missile or torpedo that fails to acquire its intended target is the true index of environmental data value. What is required is an oceanographic data collection system which is not rendered ineffective by cloud cover and provides good spatial distribution of data for all ocean areas. What is required, is a satellite based multi-sensor system.

4. Satellites and Sensors

SEASAT was a proof of concept multi-sensor oceanographic satellite flown by NASA in 1978. Although it failed after approximately 100 days in space, it conclusively demonstrated that important oceanographic parameters (sea surface temperature, sea surface wind, significant wave height and polar ice edge) could be accurately measured.

NOSS was the proposed follow-on to SEASAT. It was well designed with a suite of sensors that would have effectively met the operational requirements of the Navy for oceanographic data. Unfortunately when compared to the VW SEASAT, NOSS was perceived as being a Rolls Royce with matching price tag.

The sensors of immediate interest to the Navy are the microwave radiometer, the infrared imager, the radar altimeter and the radar scatterometer. Each sensor has a specific capability but also a limitation.

Occasionally it has been advocated that this sensor or that would do everything that needed to be done. Statements such as this are misleading and are indicative of a lack of understanding of the Navy operational problem. The fact is that no single sensor alone, because of its inherent limitations, can do the job. See plate 9. The infrared is an excellent sensor, but is cloud limited. The altimeter is excellent also, but gives a narrow swath of data. The microwave is all weather, but is limited by its resolution. The answer is a synergistic approach. Each sensor provides a piece of the puzzle - which when properly blended together can produce a more accurate picture of existing oceanographic conditions. This is the only approach which will allow a global, day by day mapping of ocean conditions to be maintained.

SATELLITE SENSORS

SENSOR	CAPABILITY	LIMITATION
● MICROWAVE	GLOBAL, ALL WEATHER SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE DATA	PRESENT STATE OF THE ART RESOLUTION IS COARSE
● INFRARED IMAGER	EXCELLENT INFRARED DISPLAY OF ACTUAL SHAPE OF SEA SURFACE ISOTHERMS (CAN SEE FRONTS AND EDDIES)	CLOUD FREE AREAS ONLY
● RADAR ALTIMETER	SHOWS DEPRESSIONS AND ELEVATIONS OF THE SEA SURFACE (HELPS TO IDENTIFY ACTUAL EXTENT OF FRONTS AND EDDIES)	DATA IS LIMITED BY NARROWNESS OF SWATH ON OCEAN SURFACE
● RADAR SCATTEROMETER	GLOBAL SEA SURFACE WINDS (MAGNITUDE & DIRECTION) - NEEDED TO PREDICT CHANGES IN THE SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURES	MUST USE CONVENTIONAL WIND OBSERVATIONS TO SELECT THE CORRECT SATELLITE SENSED WIND DIRECTION

SYNERGISTIC TECHNIQUE
 COMBINE DATA FROM THE FOUR SENSORS TO PRODUCE A FINE DETAIL TACTICAL PRODUCT WHICH WILL ACCURATELY REFLECT OCEAN SURFACE CONDITIONS.

PLATE 9

Plate 10 lists the important atmospheric and oceanographic parameters, and the existing or planned satellites. What we see is that the requirements for atmospheric data are fairly well covered. However, with regard to the ocean it is an entirely different story. NIMBUS is a NASA research satellite which has been scheduled to cease operation in 1982, although we are looking for an extended operation. GEOSAT is an 18 month mission with only an altimeter onboard. In short, at a time when we have identified a definite operational requirement for oceanographic data, we are at a loss to do anything about it. We simply do not have the global ocean data sensing system which is required. Thus we have proposed the Navy Remote Ocean Sensing System, shown in the last column.

OCEAN DATA SYSTEMS INC.
MONTEREY, CALIFORNIA
DECEMBER 1981

**ENVIRONMENTAL SATELLITES -
PARAMETERS MEASURED**

IMPORTANT ATMOSPHERIC AND OCEANOGRAPHIC PARAMETERS	LANDSAT	GOES	TURBO/NOAA	NIMBUS ¹	GEOSAT ²	DMS ³	NAVY REMOTE OCEAN SENSING SYSTEM (PROPOSAL)
CLOUD COVER		YES	YES			YES	
UPPER AIR WINDS							
ATMOS. VERTICAL TEMPERATURE PROFILE		YES	YES			YES	
ATMOS. VERTICAL MOISTURE PROFILE			YES			YES	
SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE (CLOUD FREE AREAS ONLY)		YES	YES			YES	
SEA SURFACE WIND				MAG. ONLY UNTIL '92		MAG. ONLY	YES
SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE (NIGHT/DAY - ALL WEATHER)				UNTIL '92 ONLY			YES
SEA ICE (COVER, THICKNESS, AGE)	COVER ONLY			UNTIL '92 ONLY		STARTING '84	YES
OCEAN WAVES (HEIGHT, DIRECTION)					'84-'88 ONLY		YES
OCEAN SURFACE TOPOGRAPHY (FRONTS AND EDGES)					'84-'88 ONLY		YES

¹ NASA RESEARCH SATELLITE (1977 - 1982), NO FOLLOW ON SATELLITE PLANNED
² SINGLE INSTRUMENT SATELLITE (ALT/METER); 1984 LAUNCH - 18 MONTH MISSION

Type of Observation	Number Needed	Cost Each	Annual Maintenance & Replacement	Initial Cost x 10 ⁶ \$	Annual Cost x 10 ⁶ \$
1. Ship, Surface	4,000	10K	25%	40	10
2. Ship, Upper Air	500	200K	100%	100	100
3. Ship, Sub-surface	500	20K	200%	10	20
4. Islands, Third World	200	250K	20%	50	10
5. Drifting Buoys	5,000	5K	30%	25	8
6. Reference Buoys, Platforms	300	100K	25%	30	8
			Totals	225	136
Program Management					5
Data Collection, Validation, Communication				35	35
			Totals	295	219

THE CONVENTIONAL TYPE PLATFORM OBSERVED DATA LISTED IS ESTIMATED TO PROVIDE ABOUT 3/4 OF THE COVERAGE AVAILABLE FROM A 1-SEASAT SATELLITE SYSTEM

PLATE 10

PLATE 11

The objective of the oceanographic satellite proposal is to satisfy the operational requirements of the Navy at minimum costs. Major cost savings can be accounted for through the use of:

- o Existing space-craft design
- o Existing sensor technology
- o Existing capabilities of the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program
- o Existing computer facilities

The proposal is to fly the N-ROSS oceanographic satellite as a third satellite in the DMS³ constellation, with plans for both global and direct read-out capabilities. At the present time there are two meteorological satellites flying in the DMS³ constellation. These satellites have both a global data collection capability (utilized at Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center) and a direct readout of cloud imagery for weather forecasting (used by ships at sea).

At some point the question often arises, "we need the environmental support, but the satellite is too expensive-why don't you expand the conventional systems (ships, buoys, etc.) for gathering the data?"

NASA funded a small study to look at this alternative. As you can see from the numbers, (plate 11) the cost of doing business from such a system (which would provide only 3/4 of the data coverage when compared to a single oceanographic satellite) would be more than 2 times as much as the proposed 250 million dollar N-ROSS oceanographic satellite in the first year of operation alone.

5. Navy Support

I have stated that there were 5 elements involved in our mission to provide tactical environmental support to the Fleet; people, computers, models, communications, and a global data base. Plate 12 re-emphasizes that point. At our oceanography centers we already have the computers, models and people. We have people stationed aboard our combatant ships, and we have under development the Tactical Environmental Support System (TESS), to provide onboard direct readout of satellite environmental data and a limited area environmental analysis and forecast capability.

**NAVAL OCEANOGRAPHY COMMAND
TACTICAL ENVIRONMENTAL SUPPORT TO THE FLEET**

PLATE 12

A global data collection system will permit Fleet Numerical Oceanography Center to provide global tactical support to Navy command centers. The regional oceanography centers will be able to "fine tune" tactical environmental products in support of specific operations - for example ASW operations in the Gulf Stream area. In a wartime scenario battle group commanders must be able to stand alone. A shipboard direct readout capability from the satellite, coupled with TESS will provide the commander with an accurate

analysis of prevailing conditions within a certain radius of operations (say for example 1000 nautical miles). Good communications is a Navy-wide concern, and N-ROSS would not significantly increase the communications load to the Fleet. As mentioned previously, the Achilles heel is the global data base. It simply does not exist.

In summary there is a clear operational requirement for accurate global oceanographic data. Global ocean coverage without satellites is extremely poor. National funding for ocean sensing compared with the atmosphere has been relatively insignificant. No single oceanographic sensor can solve the Navy problem by itself.